

Filename: Nugen-RNA library 1_12.HSD5000

Gel Images

Samples

- patient_site_day-of-sampling
- 1 : 3_ETA_3
- 2 : 3_ETA_9
- 3 : 3_BAL_11
- 4 : 6_ETA_3
- 5 : 6_ETA_9
- 6 : 4_ETA_3
- 7 : 4_ETA_9
- 8 : 9_ETA_3
- 9 : 9_ETA_9
- 10 : 7_ETA_3
- 11 : 7_ETA_9
- 12 : TN1

Default image (Contrast 50%), Image is Scaled to Sample, Image is Scaled to view larger Molecular Weight range

Sample Info

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L1	2170	Ladder		Ladder
A6	4160	1		
B6	14600	2		
C6	6670	3		
D6	15700	4		
E6	11900	5		
F6	11700	6		
G6	35300	7		
H6	19600	8		
A7	22700	9		
L2	2190	Ladder		Ladder
B7	23000	10		
C7	37800	11		
D7	2220	12		

L1: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L1	2170	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	396	-	40600	-		Lower Marker
100	203	-	3120	9.35		
250	245	-	1510	11.28		
400	253	-	973	11.65		
600	277	-	710	12.76		
1000	269	-	414	12.39		
1500	229	-	235	10.56		
2500	245	-	151	11.31		
3500	248	-	109	11.45		
5000	201	-	61.7	9.25		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A6: 1

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A6	4160	1		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	256	-	26300	-		Lower Marker
247	4160	-	26000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B6: 2

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B6	14600	2		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	185	-	19000	-		Lower Marker
309	14600	-	72600	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C6: 3

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C6	6670	3		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	275	-	28200	-		Lower Marker
293	6670	-	35000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D6: 4

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D6	15700	4		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	200	-	20500	-		Lower Marker
325	15700	-	74200	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

E6: 5

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E6	11900	5		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	247	-	25400	-		Lower Marker
312	11900	-	58700	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

F6: 6

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F6	11700	6		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	261	-	26800	-		Lower Marker
310	11700	-	57800	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

G6: 7

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G6	35300	7		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	131	-	13400	-		Lower Marker
331	32000	-	149000	90.70		
960	3280	-	5250	9.30		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

H6: 8

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
H6	19600	8		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	239	-	24500	-		Lower Marker
295	19600	-	102000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A7: 9

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A7	22700	9		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	229	-	23500	-		Lower Marker
311	22700	-	112000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

L2: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L2	2190	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	410	-	42100	-		Lower Marker
100	215	-	3310	9.85		
250	256	-	1570	11.69		
400	260	-	999	11.88		
600	290	-	743	13.25		
1000	271	-	417	12.39		
1500	228	-	233	10.41		
2500	233	-	143	10.65		
3500	238	-	104	10.86		
5000	197	-	60.6	9.02		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B7: 10

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B7	23000	10		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	184	-	18900	-		Lower Marker
308	23000	-	115000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C7: 11

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C7	37800	11		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	27.6	-	2830	-		Lower Marker
336	35300	-	161000	93.30		
607	2530	-	6420	6.70		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D7: 12

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D7	2220	12		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	421	-	43100	-		Lower Marker
284	1880	-	10200	84.32		
997	349	-	538	15.68		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker